

In one season approximately 10% of the seedlings were destroyed by larval attack. In the 1970–71 and 1971–72 seasons, when attacks were heaviest, even fields with almost 100% deadhearts recovered reasonably well. No significant differences in yield were found between sprayed and unsprayed fields. An attack by *Diopsis* larvae can have positive or negative effects on the growth of rice, depending on time and level of attack, general growing conditions, and rice variety. ❧

***Shirakiacris shirakii*, a new pest of paddy in Pakistan**

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Several species of grasshoppers damage paddy in Pakistan but *Shirakiacris shirakii* was found for the first time. Its distribution is restricted to the hilly areas of Swat, Hazara, and had Kashmir, where the annual temperature is 17 to 18.5°C, annual precipitation is 950 to 1,730 mm, and elevation is 1,000 to 1,500 m. The pest is abundant in those areas. Adults are collected only from paddy, but nymphs are occasionally found on *Trifolium alexandrinum* and *Cynodon dactylon*. The insect remains associated with paddy throughout its life; nymphs feed on the leaves and adults feed on both leaves and grains. It seems to damage paddy considerably, especially in the earing stage when adults eat immature grains. The insect usually inhabits those fields where *Oxya multidentata* and *Hieroglyphus banian*, two other serious pests of paddy, are found. It feeds and develops on young maize and sorghum plants in the laboratory.

S. shirakii is a univoltine species. The eggs overwinter and hatch in May at about 24.5°C. Nymphs feed on rice nurseries and *C. dactylon*, and become adults in August or September. Oviposition begins a month later and continues until November. Several copulating pairs of *S. shirakii* have been seen on sunny November days in the harvested paddy fields, but on cloudy days they hide in

rice stubble or plant trash. Females are mostly gravid during this period and die after laying eggs. Neither adults nor nymphs could be collected from December to April; they cannot tolerate the severe cold winter. Egg pods are laid before winter – usually in the fields, preferably in sandy soil but seldom on levees. Each egg pod is buried in the soil at a depth of 2.5 to 5 cm and contains 24 to 45 eggs, averaging 39. The eggs are deep brown in color, and the froth plug is dirty brown.

The incubation period at 31 °C ranges from 17 to 23 days, averaging 20 days. Six instars of nymphal development are completed in 86 to 103 days (av. of 92 days), at about 23°C and 77% relative humidity. ❧

Outbreak of rice hispa in Nellore district, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Dicladyspa armigera, commonly known as rice hispa, is a major rice pest. Until recently, it had not been observed in the southern districts, but a severe outbreak was noted at the Regional Rice Research Station farm and many other parts of Nellore during the late kharif season, 1975–76. The main crop in Nellore – the locally evolved variety Bulk H9 (Molagolukulu) – was heavily infested.

The pest appears to have migrated from the northern districts from mid-November 1975 to the end of January 1976, after heavy rains in late October and early November 1975. After the rains, the prevailing high humidity and intermittent bright sunshine seem to have favored hispa development in epidemic proportions. The maximum temperature during the day never exceeded 29°C, and the minimum ranged between 17 and 20°C until the end of January 1976. Toward the end of January, a decline in the beetle population occurred synchronously with the rise in temperatures and the lowering of the relative humidity. Hispa exhibited a

Entries in the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) and the National Screening Nursery (NSN) with less than 1% of the leaf area damaged by rice hispa. Andhra Pradesh, India.

IRON	
IR2053-375-1-1-5	RD5
IR2058-74-2-1-1	Chianung-Sen 11
IR2063-152-3-2	B 452b-290-2-1-3
IR2063-185-2-2	Pelita 1-2
IR2068-65-3	C 168-134
Purple check 15/ IRI 103-1	IR2153-26-3-5-6 Bahagia (R check)
IR2070-178-2-3	IR1545-339-2-2
IR2070-210-3-3-4	IR2070-199-3-6-6
IR2070-288-2-2-5	IR22 (S check)
IR2070-614-6-4	IR5491-4-80 (Gihl)
IR2070-796-1-4-3	RPW 6-2
IR2070-834-1-2	IR20
BW 196	IR2153-15-1-10-3
BKN 6323-17	IR2031-114-2-3-1
BKN 6819-33-3-2-1-3	IR2153-26-3-5-2
BKN 6819-33-3-2-2-3	M1 48
BKN 6820-4-1-3	IET 1444
BKN 6820-6-3-2	
NSN	
RP 633-382-1-1-5-7	R 19-1-1-1
RP 974-97-8-1	R 45-1-2-2
R 8-2-4-1	R 49-2-2-2-1-1-1
R 8-12-1-1	

marked preference for younger plants.

Damage was also observed on many entries from the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) and the National Screening Nursery (NSN) trials, which were exposed to the large hispa population (see table). The severity of the epidemic is clear: more than 25% of the leaf area was lost in half of the IRON entries and in 95% of the NSN entries. Eight sprays were used consecutively from early November, almost at weekly intervals: Ambithion, Folithion, Sumithion, Sumithion with BHC, Sumithion with Endrin, and three sprays of Sevin with BHC. They were, however, effective only for 2 or 3 days. After that period, the hispa population rose to the original level, probably because of invasions of fresh insects from adjacent fields where no control measures were undertaken.

Various spray schedules were followed on the blast-susceptible variety BCP 1 to evaluate the effects of Phosvel 34% EC (*O*. 2,5 Dichloro-4 bromopheny 1) *O*-methyl phenylphosphonothionate) on blast. Although hispa severely damaged

the unsprayed control plot as well as the surrounding plots, it produced no damage in any of the Phosvel-treated plots. ❧

Effects of soaking seeds in chemicals on the control of root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

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Seeds of IR8 were soaked in a 4-ml test solution of each of 32 chemicals at doses of 500, 1,000, and 2,000 ppm for 12 and 24 h, or equivalent to doses of 0.2, 0.4, and 0.8 g/100 g seed with water control. Treated seeds were sown in soil inoculated with infective larvae of

M. graminicola. Nematicides and insecticides were effective to varying degrees in reducing the endoparasites and egg mass production. Among fungicides, only thiobendazole was effective (see table). Herbicides were phytotoxic; growth regulators and hormones were less effective; amino acids were ineffective. Oxamyl, fensulfothion, and phorate reduced endoparasites by more than 60% and egg masses by 80%. Carbofuran inhibited endoparasites, but was less effective in reducing egg mass production. Oxamyl at 500 and 1,000 ppm was as effective as other chemicals at higher doses either as 12- or 24-h seed-soak treatment. All herbicides affected seed viability and hormones, and growth regulators affected growth. ❧

Effects of soaking seeds in pesticides on invasion and development of *Meloidogyne graminicola*. Minimum nematode incidence at 2,000 ppm.

Treatment	Endoparasites (no.)	Egg masses (no.)	Germination (%)
<i>Nematicides and insecticides</i>			
Oxamyl	15.0	2.2	100
DBCP	23.1	5.5	100
Chlorpyrifos	18.0	6.1	100
Phorate	18.5	3.2	100
Carbofuran	30.2	3.2	100
Mephospholan	31.2	9.2	100
Fensulfothion	18.0	3.5	100
Quinalphos	25.1	7.1	95
<i>Fungicides</i>			
Mebenil	52.5	15.0	100
Bavistin	54.0	16.2	100
Thiabendazole	39.5	14.1	85
Cela - 50	50.0	16.5	92
Control	51.2	17.7	100

Whitebacked planthopper outbreak in Bangladesh

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The whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* is a minor rice pest in Bangladesh. Two outbreaks of the pest were recorded in deep-water rice in 1963 (March–December and May–June). In 1967, the pest occurred in aus rice (March–August) and in deep-water rice during July in Comilla district. During the early 1970's, the pest was the

dominant hopper in the aus season in Mymensingh area, making up 61% of the total hopper population. But during the transplanted aman season (July–December), it ranked fourth and made up about 10% of the population.

In mid-April 1977, hopperbum due to *S. furcifera* was observed on the boro season crop (November–May) of IR8 in a patch of 55.74 sq m in the Mohammadpur area of Dacca. The crop was in the milky to dough stage; the plot was irrigated by sewage water. The population on 18 April was more than 1,000 adults and nymphs/hill. Loss was estimated at about 80% of the expected yield. ❧

Parasites of grasshopper eggs associated with paddy in Pakistan

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Scelio spp. are important parasites of grasshopper eggs. Six species parasitize grasshoppers that attack paddy in Pakistan. The widely distributed and adaptable parasites can withstand severely cold winters by hibernating as first-instar larvae in the host eggs. In summer the parasite adults are found mostly in shady places where they are protected from excessive heat; when dense vegetation is lacking, they creep into crevices.

Scelio do not parasitize all eggs in large egg pods, but egg pods with no more than 25 eggs are completely parasitized. Freshly laid host eggs are preferred to old ones.

The patchy distribution of host eggs may not allow enough of the parasites to develop to provide a high level of grasshopper control. Although *Scelio* do not seem to play a dominant role, they are in position to eliminate many eggs in the late fall. That could reduce the nymphal population in the spring and result in fewer adults in the summer. ❧

Subsequent infectivity of treated *Meloidogyne* larvae in chemicals

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Larvae of *Meloidogyne graminicola* were held in aerated distilled water for 24 h after direct contact for 48 h with nematicides, insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, amino acids, growth regulators, and hormones at different levels. The contact toxicity tests showed that the following chemicals resulted in more than 90% mortality: oxamyl (nematicide) and propanil (herbicide) at 50 ppm and above; fensulfothion (insecticide) at 100 ppm; quinalphos (insecticide) and DBCP (nematicide) at 200 ppm; ZR-777 (hormone) at 500 ppm; and cycocel (growth regulator) at 1,000 ppm. DL forms of amino acids, fungicides, and other growth regulators were